

Sexting and Sextortion Among Czech Adolescents: A Case-Based Qualitative Analysis

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Abstract

The rise of digital communication has fundamentally reshaped adolescent social interactions, bringing new risks alongside new forms of intimacy. This study investigates the psychosocial dynamics of sexting and sextortion among children and adolescents aged 10 to 17, drawing on 416 anonymized case reports submitted to the Czech E-Bezpečí online counseling service between 2013 and 2025. Using qualitative coding and thematic analysis, the study explores patterns of behavior, underlying motivations, relationship dynamics, and psychological consequences associated with consensual sexting and coercive sextortion.

Findings indicate that sexting is most prevalent between ages 15–17, often driven by romantic motivations, peer influence, or emotional exploration. A statistically significant association was found between gender and type of case, highlighting divergent risk profiles. The majority of perpetrators were strangers or online acquaintances, although ex-partners and current friends also played a role, reflecting both opportunistic and relational abuse dynamics.

Psychological impacts were profound. Victims reported anxiety, shame, suicidal ideation, and social withdrawal, often in response to breaches of trust or public humiliation. The emotional toll was compounded by fears of legal repercussions and the irreversible circulation of explicit content. Notably, many victims reached out preemptively, fearing potential dissemination, illustrating how anticipated harm can drive distress even without actual exposure.

Introduction

The digital era has ushered in unprecedented opportunities for communication and self-expression, particularly among children and adolescents, yet this increased connectivity also presents novel challenges, notably in the realms of sexting and sextortion. Sexting (the sharing, sending, or receiving of sexually explicit messages, photographs, or videos via digital communication tools, particularly mobile phones, social media platforms, and messaging applications) is increasingly recognized as a common behavior among adolescents, particularly in the context of online romantic interactions, and may in some cases be misused and lead to coercive practices such as online sextortion (Döring, 2014; Kopecký, 2017; Kopecký & Szotkowski, 2018; Radebe & Njenga, 2024). Sextortion, a more insidious phenomenon, involves the exploitation of these intimate images or information through threats, coercion, or blackmail. This can lead to severe psychological distress and potential long-term consequences for victims (Hong et al., 2020). Understanding the psychosocial dynamics, motivations, and consequences surrounding sexting and sextortion is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies.

This qualitative study delves into case reports from an online counseling service to explore the patterns, motivations, and consequences of sexting and sextortion among children and adolescents aged 10 to 17. By examining real-life scenarios documented by victims, this research aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the experiences of young people involved in these behaviors. Previous studies have noted that certain methodological constraints — such as survey environments that do not guarantee privacy — may lead to underreporting of sexting behaviors (Lenhart, n.d.; Mitchell et al., 2012). Unlike

large-scale surveys that may rely on parental reports or retrospective accounts, our analysis is grounded in the authentic and immediate testimony of a child confronting a personal problem, thus avoiding this particular limitation. This perspective allows for a more nuanced understanding of the child's lived experience and offers valuable insights for more targeted prevention and intervention strategies. This clearer understanding of psychosocial motivations and contextual risk factors is crucial for prevention and education strategies (Madigan et al., 2018; Mori et al., 2020).

Motivations and Patterns of Sexting

The prevalence of sexting among young people is increasing, with studies indicating that a significant proportion of adolescents have sent, received, or forwarded sexts (Molla-Esparza, Losilla, et al., 2020; Sztokowski et al., 2020). The patterns of sexting can vary widely, ranging from consensual exchanges between romantic partners to non-consensual dissemination of images or messages. The anonymity afforded by online platforms can contribute to a sense of disinhibition, leading adolescents to engage in behaviors they might otherwise avoid in face-to-face interactions. The lack of immediate feedback and the potential for delayed consequences can also diminish perceptions of risk, making young people more vulnerable to engaging in sexting without fully understanding the potential ramifications (Howard et al., 2023).

The motivations behind sexting among adolescents are multifaceted, spanning social, emotional, and psychological domains. Some adolescents engage in sexting as a means of sexual expression in online interactions and as part of their exploration of emerging sexuality (Sharma et al., 2019). In many cases, peer pressure – especially via social media platforms - plays a critical role in initiating such behavior. The drive to conform to group norms and maintain social status can often outweigh awareness of risks and consequences. Additionally, sexting may serve as an expression of autonomy, particularly among youth navigating restrictive cultural norms surrounding sexuality (Chege & Lumala, 2020).

Theoretical framework

Understanding the emergence and dynamics of sexting and sextortion among adolescents requires a multidimensional theoretical approach that reflects the complexity of contemporary digital socialization. These behaviors do not occur in isolation but are embedded in a broader sociocultural and technological context where risk-taking, identity exploration, and peer influence intersect. The convergence of interpersonal communication technologies and adolescent development has transformed traditional patterns of social interaction, demanding new analytical lenses for examining behaviors such as sexting and the increasingly prevalent phenomenon of sextortion (Morelli et al., 2025).

A foundational lens for understanding sexting is **social learning theory**, which posits that behavior is acquired through observation and imitation of others, particularly within peer networks (Sesar et al., 2019). Adolescents often look to their social environment for behavioral cues, and when sexting is perceived as normative or even desirable—reinforced by peer approval or romantic attention - it becomes more likely that individuals will engage in it (Dodaj & Sesar, 2023). This aligns with findings that adolescents exposed to peers who engage in sexting are significantly more likely to adopt similar behaviors themselves, especially in the absence of critical media literacy or adult guidance.

Complementing this is **developmental vulnerability theory**, which suggests that early adverse experiences - such as neglect, abuse, or unstable family dynamics - can impair emotional regulation and lead to increased susceptibility to risky or exploitative behaviors later in adolescence (Yoder et al., 2018). For some adolescents, sexting may serve as a maladaptive coping mechanism or a form of seeking validation in response to earlier emotional wounds.

The influence of technology is further reflected in the concept of **digital natives** - young people who have grown up immersed in digital technologies. Their lived experience with instantaneous communication and online sharing often shapes a more fluid understanding of privacy and permanence,

sometimes leading to underestimation of the risks associated with sharing intimate content (Mori et al., 2020).

From a different angle, **social control theory** (Hirschi, 2017) emphasizes the protective role of strong social bonds, attachment to institutions (e.g., school, family), and internalization of norms in deterring deviant behaviors such as sexting. When these bonds are weakened—for instance, due to lack of parental involvement or social alienation—adolescents may be more prone to experimentation with risk-laden digital behaviors. This notion is reinforced by **self-control theory**, which posits that individuals with lower self-regulation are more likely to act impulsively without fully considering long-term consequences (Lee et al., 2013). In adolescence, the search for social adaptation and approval often heightens these tendencies, particularly when peer pressure promotes sexually expressive behaviors. Even when aware of potential risks, many teens still choose to engage in sexting as they navigate intimate relationships and social hierarchies (Perry et al., 2022; Tamarit et al., 2021).

Applying **social exchange theory**, as suggested by Wright & Wachs (2024) offers a compelling lens for understanding the differential outcomes of consensual versus non-consensual and pressured sexting. While consensual sexting may enhance intimacy and emotional connection (i.e., relational “rewards”), coerced or non-consensual exchanges often yield psychological “costs”, thereby contributing to mental health issues and sexual risk behaviors.

Routine activity theory further explains how sextortion opportunities arise from the convergence of three conditions: the presence of a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the absence of capable guardians (Kitteringham & Fennelly, 2020). The online environment often amplifies these factors, offering both access and anonymity to perpetrators. Research has also shown that victims with histories of trauma, sexual abuse, or chaotic domestic lives exhibit greater vulnerability to cyber victimization (Hong et al., 2020; Radebe & Njenga, 2024).

Methods

This study is based on data collected through the E-Bezpečí online counselling service, which has been operating in the Czech Republic at Palacký University in Olomouc since 2010 and has documented over 5,000 cases of risky online behavior among children and adolescents. For the purposes of the present research, we analyzed case reports submitted between **6 June 2013 and 13 February 2025**. In accordance with the platform's terms of use, respondents were informed that anonymized data might be used for research purposes. All personal information was removed in line with ethical standards for data protection and the privacy of individuals. The study received approval from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Education, Palacký University in Olomouc.

Case Selection

From the full dataset of 5,001 cases, we selected those involving children aged **10 to 17 years** and categorized them based on the type of risky online interaction. While the **primary focus** of our study was on **sexting**, we also included **sexortion cases** in the quantitative analysis to explore **gender differences** between these two forms of online sexual risk behavior. However, for the purposes of the **qualitative analysis**, we focused exclusively on cases involving **sexting without any explicit elements of extortion**. After this filtering process, a total of **133 relevant cases** were retained for in-depth qualitative examination.

Each case entry contained multiple variables: a unique case ID, the date of submission, the respondent's gender and age, a free-text narrative (typically written by the child or adolescent), and a series of researcher-assigned thematic codes. All cases were anonymized prior to analysis to ensure the ethical handling of sensitive content.

Coding Strategy

The study employed a **qualitative content analysis** approach, grounded in an **open, inductive coding process**. The primary researcher manually reviewed each case narrative line by line and assigned codes based on recurring semantic themes. These themes were not predefined but rather emerged from the data itself, in line with principles of grounded theory. All coding procedures were conducted in **Microsoft Excel**, which enabled systematic documentation and cross-case comparison of thematic categories.

The final **codebook** included a diverse range of concepts grouped into psychological, social, behavioral, and contextual dimensions. Commonly applied codes included:

- **Psychological states:** fear, psychological deterioration, self-reflection.
- **Social dynamics:** former partner, recent partner, unknown perpetrator, friend, cross-border element.
- **Behavioral and response patterns:** non-consensual dissemination, avoidance of reporting, bribery, prank.
- **Technological context:** platform-specific dissemination (Facebook etc.), general modes of sharing (direct messaging, web posting etc).
- **Platform-specific dissemination:** (e.g., Instagram, Facebook, Pornhub, Ask.fm, Omegle) or general modes of sharing such as *zprávy* (direct messaging) and *web* (public web posting).

Each case could be assigned multiple codes to capture the complexity of the situation. For example, a case *coded with fear, unknowb, and sharing* would indicate a victim experiencing fear, targeted by an unknown perpetrator, and affected by the unauthorized distribution of intimate content.

Illustrative Example

"Hello. My ex-boyfriend sent my naked photos to everyone at school. I really regret sending them to him when we were together, but it's too late now. When I asked him why he did it, he said someone had accessed his phone. But I gradually found out that he did it himself. I can't understand why he did that to me. I have his photos too. I was angry and completely devastated. Under pressure from my friends, who forced me to do it, I sent his photo. I started to regret it terribly. It didn't do me any good anyway. Because everyone in the whole school has my naked photos. I want it all to disappear. But I feel like there's nothing I can do about it. So I'm writing to you to ask for advice. I can't tell anyone because he's so mean to me that he would use it against me. He probably did all this because I broke up with him. He didn't treat me nicely and gradually started swearing at me. Then he sent the photos everywhere and still does. Thank you. Goodbye."

Assigned codes: former partner; non-consensual dissemination; psychological deterioration; direct messaging

Intercoder Reliability and Collaboration

Although the initial round of coding was conducted by the lead researcher, the coding framework and assignments were subsequently **reviewed and refined collaboratively** by a team of three researchers with academic backgrounds in **education, psychology, and media studies**. Through **iterative discussion and joint calibration**, the research team ensured consistency in interpretation and classification. While formal metrics of **intercoder reliability** (such as Cohen's κ) were not calculated—due to the exploratory and interpretative nature of the dataset—the collaborative approach contributed to conceptual rigor and reliability across the coding process.

Results

The final sample included 416 relevant cases, of which 133 were categorized as sexting and 283 as sextortion. Gender distribution revealed a higher proportion of female victims in both categories.

Figure 1

Observed counts of sexting and sextortion cases by gender

Category	Girls	Boys	Not specified
Sexting	103	26	4
Sextortion	180	98	5

Proportionally, girls accounted for approximately 77 % of sexting cases and 65 % of sextortion cases, whereas boys represented 20 % and 35 %, respectively.

Figure 2

Observed vs. expected counts of sexting and sextortion cases by gender

Gender	Type	Observed	Expected
Girl	Sexting	103	89.70
Girl	Sextortion	180	193.30
Boy	Sexting	26	39.29
Boy	Sextortion	98	84.71

To examine whether this gender distribution significantly differed between the two categories, we conducted a chi-square test of independence. The results indicated a statistically significant association between gender and type of case ($\chi^2 = 8.78, p = 0.003, df = 1$), suggesting that the observed distribution is unlikely to be due to chance and reflects meaningful differences in how these behaviours manifest across genders.

Across the dataset, sexually related cyber-incidents concentrate in mid-adolescence and have intensified in recent years. Sextortion reports cluster most strongly at ages 16–17, with these two cohorts accounting for nearly one-half of all such cases, whereas consensual sexting is more evenly spread across ages 15–17 and remains uncommon outside that range, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 3

Number of sexting and sextortion cases by age

When the data are viewed longitudinally, sextortion appears to be accelerating: annual counts remain marginal until 2019 but rise continuously thereafter, reaching a five-fold increase by 2024. In contrast, sexting fluctuates modestly—never exceeding five cases per year—and shows only a brief uptick in 2023. Taken together, the evidence points to mid-adolescence as the primary risk window, with sextortion emerging as a rapidly growing threat that now outpaces sexting incidents year-on-year. This pattern is visualized in Figure 2.

Figure 3

Number of sexting and sextortion cases by year

Qualitative Findings

Motivations for Seeking Help

The most commonly cited reason for contacting the counselling service was the **non-consensual dissemination of intimate materials**, even when no explicit blackmail was involved. A total of 76 victims reported that their private content—often photographs or videos—had been shared with others without their permission. This frequently occurred despite the initial exchange being perceived as consensual, highlighting a significant breach of trust and a common trajectory from consensual sexting to victimization. One 14-year-old respondent described their experience as follows: „*A nude photo was being shared at school and I don't know if it has been deleted or not. I need to talk to someone about it because people at school keep looking at me and it's really uncomfortable.*“

In 27 responses, participants reported that the intimate material had not yet been disseminated, but they were afraid that it might be. As a result, they contacted the counselling service for advice on how to proceed. As noted by a 12-year-old boy:

“I sent nudes and now I'm afraid they might be shared. It's been about three days and nothing has appeared on my Facebook, but I deactivated it. A girl from Slovakia was contacted by a boy who said he had my videos. I blocked him and have not been in contact since.”

This example illustrates the anticipatory anxiety that can arise even in the absence of actual circulation, and the perceived loss of control that prompts children to seek support.

A smaller subset of respondents (20 cases) described situations in which they were **subjected to pressure or explicit requests for intimate content**, but ultimately did not comply. These cases demonstrate the psychological burden that coercive behaviour can impose on minors, even in the absence of actual compliance. Illustrative of this discomfort, one adolescent shared (age 14): *“Someone contacted me on Facebook and asked to be friends. I accepted the request, and about an hour later, he started asking for 'fingering' and then for pictures. He asked me if I had ever done it and asked about*

other sex-related things. He also contacted several of my classmates and girlfriends and asked them for the same. I'm not friends with him, but I think he could hurt someone, so I'm writing to you."

Another group (7 cases) contacted the counselling service to inquire about the legality of sending or possessing sexually explicit materials involving minors—these were typically individuals who had shared such materials themselves and were uncertain about the legal consequences of their actions. In some instances, concern was expressed on behalf of others, particularly peers or romantic partners, reflecting an awareness of potential criminal liability even in ambiguous or peer-to-peer contexts. As described by a 15-year-old respondent: "Hello, I have a problem. I know a friend (15 years old), and I'm a bit worried about him. He had a girlfriend (13 years old), and she sent him a few nude photos (breasts, buttocks). One of the photos was seen by his female friend, and later some others by another male friend. The girlfriend found out and broke up with him. Her father found out about it after half a year. Do you think he could face legal consequences? If so, what kind? Thank you."

Modes of Dissemination

The methods by which intimate materials were disseminated varied considerably. In most cases (49), the content was shared via direct messaging, often through social media or private chat applications. However, in 11 particularly serious cases, materials were made publicly accessible on widely used platforms such as Facebook, Ask.fm, Pornhub, or Instagram Stories.

One illustrative case involved a 17-year-old girl who reported the following situation:

"Hello, I would like to turn to you with the following problem. About a year ago, I sent a semi-nude photo to my then ex-boyfriend, and yesterday it appeared on the social network Ask.fm along with anonymous comments threatening to send it to my current partner. I wanted to ask if there is any way to remove this material from circulation, because the whole situation is very distressing to me."

Figure 3

A concept map illustrating the reasons why children seek help from the counselling service, as well as the main channels through which intimate materials are disseminated.

Coercion and Victim Response

An important subset of cases (38) involved **coercion or pressure to send sexually explicit materials**. The gender breakdown of victims in these cases showed a clear majority of girls (31), followed by boys (5), with 2 cases where gender could not be determined. The **perpetrators were predominantly male**, although one case involved same-sex coercion (a boy pressuring another boy), and one involved an adult male who attempted to manipulate and exploit a 9-year-old boy—an incident consistent with online grooming dynamics.

Out of the 38 cases of coercion, 18 victims **complied with the request** (14 girls and 4 boys), while 20 chose **not to comply** (18 girls, 1 boy, and 1 unspecified). This distribution suggests notable gender-based differences in resistance: **boys were more likely to comply under pressure (80%)**, whereas **girls showed greater resistance, with only 44% complying**. While girls were more frequently targeted, they also demonstrated comparatively higher resilience in these situations.

Relationship to the Perpetrator

The nature of the relationship between the victim and the individual involved in the sexting incident varied widely. In the majority of cases (79), the other person was described as **an unknown or unfamiliar individual**, often referred to by the respondents in vague terms such as “some guy” or “a girl I didn’t really know.” However, a significant number of cases (16) involved a **former romantic partner**, indicating that even intimate relationships are not immune to breaches of trust and non-consensual dissemination. A typical example of this type of case is as follows (female, 14 years): *“I was stupid and sent pictures of myself in underwear... to my ex-boyfriend, and now he’s sending them everywhere and showing them around. What should I do???”*

In 12 cases, the sexting exchange occurred between **friends**, while 6 cases were linked to interactions **within the same school class**. Particularly concerning were 5 cases where **the intimate materials were distributed by a current partner**, highlighting betrayal within ongoing relationships. In a few incidents, the leak was **initiated by the victims themselves**, either accidentally (e.g., through public Instagram stories) or intentionally (e.g., posting content to a group or public website), which further complicates the victim-perpetrator dynamic and raises important questions about self-exposure and digital literacy.

Psychological Distress and Emotional Impact

Testimonies from adolescents who have experienced negative online encounters reveal an alarming level of psychological distress closely associated with such incidents. The sharing of intimate content, breaches of trust, and the threat of exposure of sensitive materials often provoke a wide range of emotional and psychological reactions that can significantly affect an individual’s mental well-being. Through our analysis, we identified recurring patterns that point to a profound disruption of personal integrity and psychological balance.

One of the most frequently reported consequences was **persistent anxiety and fear of potential disclosure**. Many adolescents described a pervasive sense of uncertainty, loss of control, and fear of future consequences. Statements such as *“I’m scared I’ll say something wrong and he’ll just post it online for no reason,”* or *“I don’t know what to do—I’m terrified,”* illustrate how the mere possibility of digital exploitation can paralyze everyday functioning and mental stability.

Feelings of **shame and guilt** were also commonly observed, often emerging as a retrospective self-evaluation of one’s actions. Adolescents frequently internalized the blame for sharing intimate content and assumed personal responsibility for the aftermath. This is exemplified by comments such as *“How could I have made such a mistake?”* or *“I know it’s my fault, but I didn’t realize what could happen at the time.”* However, these reflections often obscure the reality that the core wrongdoing lies in the perpetrator’s misuse of trust and power.

Among the most serious outcomes were **suicidal ideation and self-harming behaviors**. Several participants expressed profound despair and a sense of helplessness. For instance, statements like *“I want to die. I have no reason to live anymore,”* or *“I cut myself... I don’t know what to do. I blame myself so much,”* indicate acute psychological suffering and a cry for help that must not be ignored.

Symptoms of **low self-esteem and depression** often manifested as long-term consequences of repeated humiliation, bullying, or unresolved trauma. Victims frequently reported a decline in self-confidence, social withdrawal, and emotional apathy. One respondent wrote, *“I have a serious problem with my self-esteem... he was the only one who understood me, and now he just insults me,”* while another stated, *“Every day I feel awful. I don’t want to eat or drink. I’ve hit rock bottom.”*

A critical factor underlying many of these cases was **manipulation and emotional blackmail**. Offenders often exploited the victim's emotional dependence, loneliness, or need for acceptance. Examples include: *“He said if I didn’t send him some photos, he’d stop talking to me,”* and *“He messaged me, ‘watch out—I have your nudes,’ just because I blocked him.”* Such testimonies demonstrate how easily trust can be weaponized for psychological coercion.

The consequences of such experiences extended beyond internal emotional distress. Many participants also reported instances of **cyberbullying and public humiliation**, which had concrete repercussions in their everyday lives. Statements like *“Everyone in my school has my naked photos,”* or *“Someone posted a picture of me in my underwear on Facebook... now everyone’s sharing it,”* reflect the severe stigma and social isolation that can follow, sometimes leading to exclusion from peer groups.

Another serious phenomenon identified was **obsessive rumination and the inability to find peace**, particularly in relation to the uncertainty of whether their private materials would be further disseminated. Adolescents described a constant state of tension and intrusive thoughts that persisted even after long periods. For example: *“For two years, every night before bed I think about it and pray that it won’t get out,”* or *“My parents know everything, but it still bothers me. I can’t find peace.”* These remarks show just how enduring and profound the psychological toll can be.

Such emotional strain often had a **direct impact on educational performance and interpersonal relationships**. Some participants reported academic decline, school transfers, or relationship breakdowns as a result of their experiences. Illustrative comments include: *“My grades dropped and I failed. I’m switching to a different school,”* and *“Because of this, he doesn’t want me anymore. Just because of the pictures.”* These examples highlight that the consequences of online sexual exploitation are not only individual and psychological, but also social and educational in nature.

Overall, these narratives demonstrate that **cyber-related trauma can reach deep into the emotional life of adolescents** and often remains hidden in their private inner world. These experiences present a compelling argument for the urgent need to develop accessible crisis intervention services, comprehensive online safety education, and sensitive communication channels tailored to young people in distress.

Discussion

A prominent finding of our analysis is that **mid-adolescence represents the peak risk window** for both sexting and sextortion incidents. Consistent with international survey data and meta-analyses, we observed that cases were largely clustered among 15 to 17-year-olds. Research consistently demonstrates that sexting behaviors increase with age throughout adolescence. A comprehensive meta-analysis found that the prevalence of sending sexts increases from approximately 4% among 12-year-olds to 9% among 14-year-olds, and further rises to 21% among 16-year-olds. (Molla-Esparza, López-González, et al., 2020) This clear age progression has been documented across multiple studies, showing that sexting becomes more common as adolescents mature (Rey et al., 2019; Tamarit et al., 2021).

Our findings regarding **gender disparities** provide an important point of comparison with existing research. We found that a substantial majority of victims in both sexting (78%) and sextortion (65%) cases were female. In their study, Wolak et al., (2018) found that 91% of those who were minors at the time of the incident were female, supporting the notion that girls are often targeted and harmed in these scenarios. The literature on consensual sexting engagement, however, is mixed on gender – some studies report girls are more likely to send images (Ybarra & Mitchell, 2014) while others find boys participate more or no significant gender difference (Strassberg et al., 2013). Our data likely reflect not just participation rates, but gendered patterns in victimization and help-seeking. Adolescent girls may face greater social risks (e.g. slut-shaming, stigma) when intimate content is circulated, which in turn could drive more female victims to seek help. At the same time, our results should not obscure the fact that boys are also affected. Notably, a nationally-representative U.S. study by Patchin & Hinduja (2018) found *males were actually more likely than females* to report being sextortion victims – a surprising result given the prevailing focus on female victims. Those authors emphasize that male youth may be under-recognized victims, possibly due to lower reporting. This may help explain our finding that, when comparing the proportions of reported cases among boys and girls in the contexts of sexting and sextortion, we observe a statistically significant increase in the proportion of boys in cases of sextortion. This leads us to hypothesize that, **while girls appear to face greater pressure in relation to sexting, boys may represent a particularly vulnerable group in cases of sextortion**—especially when such incidents are associated with financial extortion. However, this hypothesis requires more thorough examination and should be substantiated by further empirical research.

The most frequent reason children contacted the counseling center was the leakage of their intimate materials, accounting for over 57% of all cases. The prevalence of non-consensual sexting behaviors is particularly concerning. Research indicates that approximately 12% of adolescents have forwarded sexts without consent, while 8.4% have had their own sexts shared without permission (Ojeda & Rey, 2021). Another common reason for reaching out to the counseling center, however, was fear of potential dissemination. This suggests that sexting often leads, over time, to feelings of personal discomfort, regret, or anxiety among those who initially engaged in it voluntarily. Such emotional responses may stem from a reassessment of the situation, evolving relational dynamics, or growing concerns about privacy and social consequences.

We also looked at **relationship between victim and perpetrator** in these incidents, and here we find an interesting divergence from some prior research. Over half of our documented cases involved *unknown or online-only acquaintances* as the ones requesting or obtaining sexual content. In other words, many victims fell prey to **online strangers or distant contacts** – for example, children groomed by adults posing as peers, or individuals met on social media who later turned exploitative. By contrast, studies in North America have often found that sextortion frequently occurs at the hands of someone the victim knows personally. In Patchin & Hinduja’s school-based survey (2018) the majority of teen sextortion scenarios unfolded “within the context of an existing friendship (romantic or otherwise)” and it was *relatively rare for the perpetrator to be a stranger*. Similarly, Wolak et al. (2018) reported that 59% of minors in their sample knew the offender in person (commonly an ex-partner or schoolmate).

The fact that our counseling-center data show an inverse pattern – *most perpetrators being unfamiliar online figures* – may reflect differences in sampling and possibly cultural context. One plausible explanation is a differing perception of what constitutes a “known person”. In our dataset, children’s reports referring to individuals as “some boy” or “some girl” were not coded as relationships involving familiarity or friendship. Nevertheless, our data do include instances in which sexting-related issues involved a former or even current romantic partner, or a peer within the child’s social circle.

Our findings reveal the profound emotional and psychological consequences that adolescents face following negative online sexual experiences. Participants’ testimonies uncovered a pattern of acute psychological distress, including anxiety, fear of exposure, and a pervasive sense of loss of control. Feelings of shame, guilt, and self-blame were frequently internalized, even when the core harm resulted from manipulation and betrayal by others. Alarming cases of suicidal ideation and self-harming behavior were reported, often in connection with emotional blackmail or public humiliation. Persistent rumination, intrusive thoughts, and social exclusion further intensified the long-term psychological burden. These effects extended beyond the internal emotional sphere to impact academic performance, peer relationships, and overall quality of life—demonstrating that such experiences have both individual and systemic consequences.

These findings are consistent with existing empirical research on the **psychosocial effects of sexting in adolescents**, which underscores the **context-dependent nature** of its impact. A review of recent studies shows that **non-consensual and pressured sexting** are strongly associated with increased symptoms of **depression, anxiety, self-harm, and suicidality** (Choi et al., 2016; Frankel et al., 2018; Wachs et al., 2021). Conversely, **consensual sexting**, when occurring in the context of mutual trust and emotional safety, is generally **not associated with negative mental health outcomes** and may reflect aspects of normative sexual development (Alonso & Romero, 2019).

Moreover, adolescent sexting—particularly when non-consensual—has been linked to externalizing behaviors, including substance use and delinquency, compounding the risk of broader psychosocial dysfunction (Mori et al., 2019; Ybarra & Mitchell, 2014). Literature also indicates that girls are more vulnerable to coercion and its consequences, and that younger adolescents and LGBTQ+ youth face heightened risks due to social marginalization, power imbalances, and emotional dependency (Dully et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2019; Ševčíková, 2016).

It is important to note that in interpreting the role of sexting within adolescent development, some scholars (Van Dijck et al., 2025) argue that not all sexting is inherently harmful; in certain peer contexts, it may even serve identity-building or exploratory functions. However, the potential for harm significantly increases in non-consensual or coercive scenarios. This distinction reinforces the importance of context-sensitive assessments and interventions.

Altogether, both our qualitative analysis and the broader research evidence suggest that the **psychological harm caused by sexting is not inherent to the behavior itself**, but rather **emerges from power imbalances, coercion, and betrayal of trust**. This reinforces the need for **preventive strategies** that focus on **digital consent education, emotional resilience, and supportive environments** where young people can safely seek help without fear of shame or punishment.

Implications for Prevention and Intervention

Comparing our results with the broader research base leads to several implications for how educators, parents, and policymakers should address adolescent sexting and sextortion:

Comprehensive Education on Digital Consent: There is consensus that teens require better education about the risks of sexting and the importance of digital consent and privacy. Our evidence of trusted partners turning into perpetrators underscores that adolescents must be taught that **once an image is shared, control is lost**, and even people they trust could misuse it. Many countries have begun school programs on respectful online relationships; these should include discussions of sextortion scenarios. Emphasizing that *pressure to share intimate content is never okay* – whether from a friend or an online stranger – can empower youth to say no and recognize coercive red flags (as suggested by Social Learning Theory and peer-norm interventions). Education should also cover practical skills, like not sharing passwords or storing sensitive media in secure, private locations.

Peer Influence and Bystander Intervention: Given the strong peer dimensions (both positive and negative) in sexting behaviors, leveraging peer influence is crucial. Research shows that adolescents are heavily influenced by perceived peer norms (Stanley et al., 2018). If sexting appears “normalized,” more will engage; conversely, if non-consensual forwarding is stigmatized among youth, it may deter potential perpetrators. Schools and youth organizations can cultivate a culture where **sharing someone’s nudes without permission is seen as a grave betrayal** rather than a trivial prank. Bystander intervention programs could encourage teens to speak up or seek help if they know a friend is being victimized, helping overcome the isolation many victims feel.

Targeted Support for At-Risk Groups: Prevention efforts should be inclusive of groups shown to have higher risk, such as LGBTQ+ teens and those with prior trauma. Anti-bullying and digital citizenship programs must explicitly address homophobic cyber-abuse and the way sexual minority youth might be targeted (for example, being threatened with “outing” intimate images). Likewise, professionals working with youth (teachers, counselors, pediatricians) should be alert to the possibility that a teen exhibiting anxiety or depression – especially those with a history of abuse – might be experiencing online sexual exploitation. Culturally sensitive campaigns can ensure that messages reach diverse communities globally, recognizing that sextortion is a worldwide issue.

Improving Reporting Mechanisms: Both our study and prior research reveal that adolescents face significant barriers to reporting sextortion. Therefore, improving **trusted reporting mechanisms** is vital. This includes training school counselors and healthcare providers to handle disclosures non-judgmentally, publicizing confidential helplines, and perhaps integrating reporting functions into social media platforms themselves. Law enforcement agencies worldwide are beginning to designate units to combat sextortion; however, teens will only come forward if they trust that they will be protected from blame. Ensuring that youth know that possessing a sexual image of oneself is not a crime (for the minor) and that help can be obtained without automatic legal punishment is key to encouraging earlier intervention. As Patchin et al. (2020) note, cultivating a “healthy dose of skepticism” in teens regarding online sharing is important, but equally important is convincing them that if something does go wrong, seeking help is safe and worthwhile.

Legal and Platform Accountability: Our findings of perpetrators freely posting victims’ images on popular platforms (from Facebook to Pornhub) point to a need for stronger and swifter responses from tech companies. Image-based sexual abuse should be swiftly actionable – e.g. rapid content takedown and banning of offenders – to limit the spread of harmful material. Some jurisdictions have criminalized non-consensual pornography and sextortion specifically; aligning legal frameworks globally can send a clear message that **sextortion is a serious crime** with real consequences. International cooperation is also critical, since, as we saw, many sextortion cases transcend borders. The rise in sextortion reports has pushed organizations like Interpol and the FBI to issue warnings and guides in recent years. Radebe

& Njenga's (2024) bibliometric study shows an expanding knowledge base in cybersecurity circles about detecting and preventing sextortion scams. Our study adds a nuanced child-centered perspective to this discussion, reinforcing that any tech or legal solution must account for the developmental and psychological realities of adolescent victims.

Limitations and Future Directions

While comparing our results with existing literature, it is important to acknowledge the unique methodology of our study and its inherent limitations. Unlike large-scale surveys or school-based samples employed in many of the cited works, our data are derived from cases submitted to an online counseling service. As such, the sample likely skews toward incidents that were **severe enough or emotionally distressing enough to prompt help-seeking behavior**, and may underrepresent the more "hidden" or unreported cases where adolescents remain silent.

In this context, **selection bias warrants particular attention**. The sample most likely reflects a specific subgroup of youth—those who are able to recognize their experience as problematic, possess sufficient digital literacy to navigate online support systems, and feel safe or motivated to disclose their experiences to an institutional or adult figure.

This presents a risk of **underrepresenting highly vulnerable populations**, such as adolescents from socially excluded or marginalized communities, those exposed to domestic violence, or youth with insecure attachment or trauma histories—groups that may be less inclined or less able to seek formal support. Prior research has shown that such individuals are often reluctant to disclose sensitive experiences, which may lead to the **systematic omission of the most severe, chronic, or exploitative forms of sextortion**, including instances involving online grooming or commercial abuse.

Consequently, the dataset may inadvertently **overrepresent cases in which victims demonstrate proactive coping strategies** and underrepresent instances of chronic victimization, paralysis, or silence. Acknowledging this limitation would enhance the interpretive depth of the findings and support the development of **more inclusive prevention and intervention strategies**, particularly those targeting "silent victims" who may remain outside the reach of existing support infrastructures.

For instance, the lower proportion of peer-perpetrated sextortion in our data (relative to some U.S. studies) could be due to help-seeking patterns rather than actual incidence rates. Additionally, cultural factors in the Czech Republic (where our data were collected) might influence sexting norms and reporting – global generalization should therefore be done with caution. However, the strength of our approach is in capturing **rich, real-time narratives** that many surveys miss due to privacy or recall biases. Our findings complement survey-based research by adding depth on *how* and *why* these situations unfold and how adolescents feel in the moment of crisis. Future research could build on this by conducting **cross-cultural comparisons** – for example, are patterns of sextortion in counseling datasets similar in different countries? It would also be valuable to explore the role of emerging technologies (encrypted messaging, disappearing photos, deepfakes) in sexting and sextortion, as these evolve rapidly.

In conclusion, this study's results cohere with the global understanding that sexting among adolescents, while often consensual, can precipitate grave risks when digital content is misused through sextortion. By juxtaposing our findings with prior research, we see clear consensus on certain points: mid-to-late teens are most at risk, girls (and other vulnerable groups) disproportionately suffer, and the psychological fallout is severe and enduring. At the same time, our work highlights nuances such as the prominence of anonymous online predators in facilitating sextortion, a trend that may be increasing worldwide alongside the growing connectivity of youth. These insights reinforce calls by experts to treat sextortion as an urgent public health and safety issue. A multi-pronged effort – combining education, peer-led initiatives, accessible support services, and robust legal-tech measures – is needed to mitigate the harm. By comparing our results with the broader literature, we underscore that the fight against

adolescent sextortion must be **global and collaborative**, drawing on evidence and strategies from around the world to protect young people as they navigate the opportunities and perils of the digital age.

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Literature

- Alonso, C., & Romero, E. (2019). Conducta de sexting en adolescentes: predictores de personalidad y consecuencias psicosociales en un año de seguimiento. *Anales de Psicología*, 35(2), 214–224. <https://doi.org/10.6018/analesps.35.2.339831>
- Chege, S. K., & Lumala, M. (2020). A holistic framework for addressing ‘safe’ sexting challenges in Kenya. *Journal of Development and Communication Studies*, 7, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jdcs.v7i1-2.1>
- Choi, H., Ouytsel, J. Van, & Temple, J. (2016). Association between sexting and sexual coercion among female adolescents. *Journal of Adolescence*, 53, 164–168. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27814493>
- Dodaj, A., & Sesar, K. (2023). Sexting coercion within romantic context: a test of Akers social learning theory. *Journal of Sexual Aggression*, 30(2), 197–210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552600.2023.2182377>
- Döring, N. (2014). Consensual sexting among adolescents: Risk prevention through abstinence education or safer sexting? *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.5817/CP2014-1-9>
- Dully, J., Walsh, K., Doyle, C., & O’Reilly, G. (2023). Adolescent experiences of sexting: A systematic review of the qualitative literature, and recommendations for practice. *Journal of Adolescence*, 95(6), 1077–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jad.12181>
- Frankel, A. S., Bass, S. B., Patterson, F., Dai, T., & Brown, D. (2018). Sexting, Risk Behavior, and Mental Health in Adolescents: An Examination of 2015 Pennsylvania Youth Risk Behavior Survey Data. *Journal of School Health*, 88(3), 190–199. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12596>
- Hirschi, T. (2017). Causes of delinquency. In *Causes of Delinquency*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315081649>
- Hong, S., Lu, N., Wu, D., Jimenez, D. E., & Milanaik, R. L. (2020). Digital sextortion: Internet predators and pediatric interventions. *Current Opinion in Pediatrics*, 32(1), 192–197. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOP.0000000000000854>,
- Howard, D., Jarman, H. K., Clancy, E. M., Renner, H. M., Smith, R., Rowland, • Bosco, Toumbourou, J. W., Fuller-Tyszkiewicz, M., & Klettke, B. (2023). Sexting Among Australian Adolescents: Risk and Protective Factors. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 52, 2113–2130. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-023-01827-1>
- Kim, S., Martin-Storey, A., Drossos, A., Barbosa, S., & Georgiades, K. (2019). Prevalence and Correlates of Sexting Behaviors in a Provincially Representative Sample of Adolescents. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 65, 401–408. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743719895205>
- Kitteringham, G., & Fennelly, L. J. (2020). Environmental crime control. *Handbook of Loss Prevention and Crime Prevention*, 207–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817273-5.00019-3>
- Kopecký, K. (2017). Online Blackmail of Czech Children Focused on “Sextortion” (Analysis of Culprit and Victim Behaviors). *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(1), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2016.04.004>
- Kopecký, K., & Szotkowski, R. (2018). Sexting in the Population of Children and Its Risks : A Quantitative Study. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 12(2), 376–391. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3365620>

- Lee, C.-H., Moak, S., & Walker, J. T. (2013). Effects of Self-Control, Social Control, and Social Learning on Sexting Behavior Among South Korean Youths. *Youth and Society*, 48(2), 242–264. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118x13490762>
- Lenhart, A. (n.d.). *Teens and Sexting | Pew Research Center*. Retrieved May 30, 2025, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2009/12/15/teens-and-sexting/>
- Mitchell, K. J., Finkelhor, D., Jones, L. M., & Wolak, J. (2012). Prevalence and Characteristics of Youth Sexting: A National Study. *Pediatrics*, 129(1), 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.1542/PEDS.2011-1730>
- Molla-Esparza, C., López-González, E., & Losilla, J. (2020). Sexting Prevalence and Socio-Demographic Correlates in Spanish Secondary School Students. *Sexuality Research & Social Policy*.
- Molla-Esparza, C., Losilla, J., & López-González, E. (2020). Prevalence of sending, receiving and forwarding sexts among youths: A three-level meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE*.
- Morelli, M., Ragona, A., Chirumbolo, A., Nappa, M. R., Babore, A., Trumello, C., Sciabica, G. M., & Cattellino, E. (2025). Sexting Behaviors and Fear of Missing out Among Young Adults. *Behavioral Sciences* 2025, Vol. 15, Page 454, 15(4), 454. <https://doi.org/10.3390/BS15040454>
- Mori, C., Cooke, J. E., Temple, J. R., Ly, A., Lu, Y., Anderson, N., Rash, C., & Madigan, S. (2020). The Prevalence of Sexting Behaviors Among Emerging Adults: A Meta-Analysis. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 49(4), 1103–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10508-020-01656-4>,
- Mori, C., Temple, J. R., Browne, D., & Madigan, S. (2019). Association of Sexting With Sexual Behaviors and Mental Health Among Adolescents. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 173(8), 770. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2019.1658>
- Ojeda, M., & Rey, R. Del. (2021). Lines of Action for Sexting Prevention and Intervention: A Systematic Review. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*.
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2018). Sextortion Among Adolescents: Results From a National Survey of U.S. Youth. *Sexual Abuse: A Journal of Research and Treatment*, 32, 30–54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1079063218800469>
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2020). It is Time to Teach Safe Sexting. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 66(2), 140–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JADOHEALTH.2019.10.010>
- Radebe, F., & Njenga, K. (2024). Bibliometric Mapping of Scientific Production and Conceptual Structure of Cyber Sextortion in Cybersecurity. *Social Sciences*. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusId:275202525>
- Rey, R. Del, Ojeda, M., Casas, J., Mora-Merchán, J. A., & Elipe, P. (2019). Sexting Among Adolescents: The Emotional Impact and Influence of the Need for Popularity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/31496968>
- Ševčíková, A. (2016). Girls' and boys' experience with teen sexting in early and late adolescence. *Journal of Adolescence*, 51(1), 156–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.06.007>
- Sharma, M. K., Marimuthu, P., Anand, N., N, S., P, T., Thakur, P. C., Singh, P., & Gupta, H. (2019). Sexting and Self-Esteem Among Youth: Preliminary Trend for Building Cyberliteracy. *Journal of Psychosexual Health*, 1(3–4), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2631831819890768>
- Stanley, N., Barter, C., Wood, M., Aghtaie, N., Larkins, C., Lanau, A., & Överlien, C. (2018). Pornography, Sexual Coercion and Abuse and Sexting in Young People's Intimate Relationships:

- A European Study. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 33(19), 2919–2944. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260516633204>
- Strassberg, D. S., McKinnon, R. K., Sustaíta, M. A., & Rullo, J. (2013). Sexting by high school students: An exploratory and descriptive study. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 42(1), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10508-012-9969-8/TABLES/1>
- Szotkowski, R., Kopecký, K., & Dobešová, P. (2020). Sexting u českých dětí. *Sexting u Českých Děti*. <https://doi.org/10.5507/PDF.20.24457932>
- Tamarit, A., Schoeps, K., Peris-Hernández, M., & Montoya-Castilla, I. (2021). The Impact of Adolescent Internet Addiction on Sexual Online Victimization: The Mediating Effects of Sexting and Body Self-Esteem. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/bb85/9f8cae4cffacdd87815e5fd09b75834b623c.pdf>
- Van Dijck, S., Van den Eynde, S., & Enzlin, P. (2025). The bright side of sexting: A scoping review on its benefits. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2024.108499>
- Wachs, S., Wright, M. F., Gámez-Guadix, M., & Döring, N. (2021). How Are Consensual, Non-Consensual, and Pressured Sexting Linked to Depression and Self-Harm? The Moderating Effects of Demographic Variables. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(5), 2597. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18052597>
- Wolak, J., Finkelhor, D., Walsh, W., & Treitman, L. (2018). Sextortion of Minors: Characteristics and Dynamics. *The Journal of Adolescent Health: Official Publication of the Society for Adolescent Medicine*, 62(1), 72–79. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29055647>
- Wright, M. F., & Wachs, S. (2024). Longitudinal Associations between Different Types of Sexting, Adolescent Mental Health, and Sexual Risk Behaviors: Moderating Effects of Gender, Ethnicity, Disability Status, and Sexual Minority Status. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 53(3), 1115–1128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10508-023-02764-7/METRICS>
- Ybarra, M. L., & Mitchell, K. J. (2014). “Sexting” and Its Relation to Sexual Activity and Sexual Risk Behavior in a National Survey of Adolescents. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 55(6), 757–764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JADOHEALTH.2014.07.012>
- Yoder, J., Hansen, J., & Precht, M. (2018). Correlates and outcomes associated with sexting among justice involved youth: The role of developmental adversity, emotional disinhibitions, relationship context, and dating violence. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 94, 493–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.08.020>